

Interview with Virginie Rozée

Permanent Researcher at INED.

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1. What strengths do you see in the partnership between B²-InF and INED?

I see four strengths in the partnership between B²-InF and INED: (1) the issue covered by the project, (2) the international and collaborative dimension of the project, (3) the material conditions and resources offered by the project, and (4) the intended impact of the project.

INED has been working on infertility and ART issues for several years, even decades. It has significant expertise on these issues in France. Therefore, the project fits with the scientific work of INED, especially within its research unit "Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights". It provides additional expertise, considering other European countries, other target populations (young people, people who are not directly concerned by infertility and ART), and another research focus (the offers made by the clinics). These issues have not been so far addressed in INED research projects.

Then, INED is very involved in European research and committed to developing international projects, with partnerships from different countries, disciplines and sectors. These collaborations broaden the field of expertise and knowledge on a given issue or population; they allow global and transversal analysis.

The B²-InF project fits in with this determination to develop cooperative, multi-disciplinary and multi-sectoral projects. Indeed, the project is simultaneously conducted in eight European countries, including Eastern Europe countries, which are generally under-investigated in European research projects. It also brings together 10 European partners, from universities, associations, from public and private sectors, with a different expertise area and discipline.

On a more material and logistical level, B²-InF allows the partners to carry out the research in good conditions and support. One of the important objectives of INED is training in research through research. The project provides an opportunity to meet this objective as INED plans to hire a post-doctoral fellow to participate in this research.

Finally, for INED, the impact of the research in society is essential. Disseminating knowledge is indeed one of its main missions. The objective of B²-InF is to formulate recommendations based on the research results in order to inform those working in ART field (medical doctors, policy makers, civil society), to make them adapt their policies, activities and communication to be more in line with the expectations of the younger generation. Thus, the project perfectly fits with INED mission to inform social debates and policy decisions.

2. How is the purpose of this project in relation to INED?

INED is particularly involved in infertility and ART issues in the French context, where, until recently, access to ART was particularly restricted (only to heterosexual couples, for some techniques only), where infertility is still an invisible or even taboo social matter, and where fertility awareness is a very recent topic. Through our studies, we have observed an important gap between the expectations / demands of the population and the legal and medical possibilities regarding ART.

However, research at INED, like most of the research conducted on the subject around the world, mainly focuses on experiences of patients or on medical practices and offers. Very few studies explore ART knowledge and representations in the general population. These issues are nevertheless primordial to better approach and understand infertility social experience for the people concerned and the public's preconceived ideas about these recent techniques (which can lead to misunderstandings and even discrimination).

The project offers the scientific and material resources to explore all these questions at the European level, including countries that are little studied internationally. The purpose of this project is therefore to bring the INED's expertise, but above all to feed our own research and projects with the knowledge that B²-InF will bring but also with the way it is carried out, with the original methodologies and collaboration that are deployed.

I think it is the first Science with and for Society (SwafS) project conducted at INED. Therefore, we have a lot to give but also a lot to learn (even if we have a very solid International Affairs and Partnerships department).

3. Is the young society's perception towards fertility and treatments a topic of importance for INED? Why so?

At INED, many research and surveys are conducted on young people, including their sexual and reproductive lives. However, none of these studies address their perceptions of infertility and ART. Indeed, very few studies explore ART knowledge and representations in the general population, i.e. in ART non-users and people who are not, a priori, infertile. We know even less among young adults.

B²-InF will bring new knowledge to these young people, by questioning them for the first time on their knowledge and expectations regarding ART.

The results of this project will enlighten public debates, including in France, by showing the gap or, on the contrary, the match between the expectations of young people and the medical and legal possibilities in their country; young people being the future ART users and the future social actors and decision-makers.

4. The voice of society is important in this domain. Why do you think it has been relatively neglected so far?

The voice of society in the domain of infertility and ART is neglected because this issue is essentially seen as a medical one (in fact, most of the research on the subject is in the field of medicine or public health). Also because it is considered as a marginal issue, touching very few people in the general population, and as a deviant issue from the dominant social norms.

Yet, this issue concerns everyone, since it questions our representations of procreation, family formation and parenthood. This also raises questions about the normative conditions for creating a family (what we call in France the "procreative norm"), which mean that many people who want children wait until these conditions are met before conceiving a child. However, infertility is also related to the age of the future parents, both for women and men.

5. What is your opinion about the project? Method, team combination, strengths and goals?

In my opinion, B²-InF project is an important and original project. It develops an international, intersectoral and multidisciplinary approach.

Indeed, the project is simultaneously conducted in eight European countries and brings together an international team working in different but complementary fields and sectors.

Then, the project proposes a legal, gender and socio-cultural research perspective, which will allow an original global and transversal analysis. It is also a very innovative project since it analyses the offers made by the clinics, through their advertising (websites, flyers, etc.), in order to observe whether they correspond to people's expectations.

Finally, the pragmatic aspect makes the project much-needed and essential. It aims to enlighten those working in the ART field, including policy makers, so that they can adapt their policies, medical offers, practices and communication and make them better fit with the young generation's expectations.

On a more personal and human ground, the team is very nice; the meetings are very friendly and give rise to many exchanges.